

**CATEGORY OF MODALITY IN JAPANESE AND UZBEK AND
SCIENTIFIC THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS**

Temirova Muslima

Tashkent State University Of Oriental Studies

Teacher of Department of Japanese Philology

muslima.temirova.2022@gmail.com

Annotation: One of the most complex aspects of verbs in the Uzbek language, the inflectional category, has been studied by linguists such as A.G. Gulomov, A. Khojiev, and their service to science is undoubtedly incomparable. However, the following feature is clearly visible in the studies carried out on the same topic: our linguists-scientists in many cases relied on the conclusions of Russian grammarians when studying the rules and grammatical categories of the language. Due to this, in some cases, the unique aspect and essence of the Uzbek language has been neglected. In this article, we will study the Japanese and Uzbek languages definition of inclination, history of study of the inclination category, and problematic situations.

Key words: modality, category, inflectional category, essence of the Uzbek language

The problems of the internal system of the language have been thoroughly studied until the present period of the development of the science of linguistics. It can be easily observed that the studied phenomena are of great importance both in general linguistics and in specific linguistics.

It is known that in every language, the verb word group is complex in terms of character and structure, its grammatical functions are diverse, and it is the largest section in terms of volume. The mood and tense categories are the main grammatical signs of the verb. Because one of the functions of the verb in the sentence is to appear in the predicative function, and this function is realized

through mood and tense. It is known that a verb is a group of words denoting an action. In general linguistics, verb forms are divided into two types, depending on whether or not they have the characteristic of forming a system of forms specific to a certain grammatical category of the verb:

- 1) categorical;
- 2) non-categorical (functional) form;

Categorical form expresses the grammatical meanings specific to a certain category of the verb. For example, such verbs are forms that belong to the categories of degree, inclination, tense, and person-number.

Forms of the verb that are not specific to any grammatical category and are used to express different modal meanings or perform other tasks are functional, that is, non-categorical forms. For example, non-categorical (functional) forms of the verb are the repetition of the action, impulses that indicate weakness, smile, as well as adjectives, adverbs, and nouns of action. This research work is devoted to the comparative study of the category of inclination, which is one of the categories that is characteristic of the categorical form and expresses grammatical meanings.

Before talking about the category of inclination, it is important to clarify the definition of "inclination" in Japanese and Uzbek languages. It is clear from scientific sources that the term definition is a term that entered linguistics from the Latin language. In the Latin language, it means "definition", "to show clearly", that is, it means a brief scientific explanation and definition of a concept that reflects the most important signs of things and events.

In Japanese, two lexemes are used to define mood: 法(hou) and mūdo (ムード). 法(hou) means method, law, regulation, method and tendency. In monolingual and bilingual dictionaries, it was found that this word 法(hou) is explained. The second lexeme (mu-do) is often used in textbooks and theoretical manuals written in Japanese. The word 法(hou) is a word borrowed from 漢語(kango), that is, from the Chinese language, and is used in many scientific works on the Japanese

language. The second word ムード (mu-do) is borrowed from a foreign language 外来語, and is derived from the English word “mood”, i.e. “inclination”. This word is used in modern textbooks on the Japanese language. In some textbooks, it was observed that both terms appear at the same time. The word 法 (hou) is represented by one hieroglyph because it is 漢語 and ムード (mu-do) is a root word.

So, if the grammatical concept of “aspects is expressed by two words in Japanese, “mayl” is one root word in Uzbek.

In Japanese, the origin of the definitional lexeme is actually the word “simple”, and according to the grammatical meaning in Uzbek, it gives the concept of “inclination”.

In the Uzbek language, the word “mayl” came from the Arabic language and means “ability”. In many linguistic dictionaries, as well as in various scientific sources, this word is defined as follows: “The relation of action to reality is called inclination. Reality is the implementation of a certain action by a person in a certain time and space.

It is known that the meanings understood through the category of inclination are also modal meanings. Because the action expressed by the verb forms, the desire to complete the event, desire, precision, etc. are directly connected with the category of modality. But modality is broader than inclination. The category of modality, which shows the relation of thought to real reality, is expressed through other means of the language, in addition to the inflectional forms of the verb. The mood category is inextricably linked with the tense and person category and is included in the conjugation system of the verb. Determining the declension system in each language should be based on the language's own characteristics and material. In the Japanese language, the category of declension is one of the controversial issues, and there is no unanimity in the opinions of Japanese linguists and Japanese scholars regarding the types of declension and the number of forms

representing it. In the literature on Japanese linguistics, by showing five different declensions of the verb in Japanese, they create five different categories of declension.

Within this phenomenon, the views of Russian Japanese scholars are different, the essence of the category of the Japanese language and its forms are presented in different ways in the scientific works of a number of Russian Japanese scholars, such as V. Alpatov, B. Lavrentyev, V. Golovnin, V. Pryakhina, A. Kolesnikova . Including V. Alpatov in Japanese, he divides inclinations into four types, while V. Golovnin divides them into two large groups and, in turn, divides them into small groups. V. Lavrentiev, unlike them, considers each form of inclination as a group and divides them into six groups. From the above, it is natural to ask why there is no unanimity in the opinions of scientists. As a result of the observation, it can be said that in the Japanese language, at first, “tendency” was not considered as a category, but simply as a declension of a verb, and the forms of emotionality that express them in relation to reality were not considered a single category, but a separate “grammatical suffix”. Also, when the grammar of the Japanese language was studied from the point of view of general linguistics, the category of inclination was defined as $\Delta - \text{ド}$ (mu-do). The one-sidedness of the views of Russian Japanese scholars can be seen, firstly, that some of them conducted research based on Russian grammar, and secondly, the lack of person-number suffixes in the Japanese language in the manifestation of the category of inclination in the sentence. For this reason, the diversity of the Japanese language category requires a more in-depth study of this category.

We can observe the similarities and differences between the above definitions of inclination in the Japanese and Uzbek languages. The point of similarity is that in both languages it is emphasized that the category of inclination means action and state. The difference is that in Japanese, in addition to the action and state, it indicates the existence of a process and an object. We can say that the process and

existence of the subject is indicated separately in the definition of inclination given in Japanese, which is related to the culture of this language. In the Uzbek language, the process and existence of the subject are not emphasized separately, but are included in the action and state. For example, compare:

この薬を飲むと熱が下がる。 *Kono kusuri wo nomuto netsu ga sagaru.*

この薬を飲めば熱が下がる。 *Kono kusuri wo nomeba netsu ga sagaru.*

この薬を飲んだら熱が下がる。 *Kono kusuri wo nondara netsu ga sagaru.*

この薬を飲むなら/飲んだなら熱が下がる。 *Kono kusuri wo nomunara/nondanara netsu ga sagaru*

In these sentences, “if he drinks medicine” is expressed by the Japanese noun “to drink” with a four-point category. In the Uzbek language, the above four sentences only mean the conditional meaning.

From the above, it can be seen that the definition of slope is expressed by different expressions. In Japanese, it is expressed by the two words 法 (hou) and ムード (mu-do), while in Uzbek, it is expressed by a single word. So, in terms of structure, it is shown that this phenomenon is different in both languages. Nevertheless, one commonality is noticeable in expressing the meaning of the definition of inclination in both languages, that is, the words expressing the concept of inclination in Japanese and Uzbek languages are lexemes borrowed from foreign languages. Japanese lexemes are taken from Chinese and English, while modality in Uzbek is a word borrowed from Arabic.

Also, despite the fact that the category of inclination is a comprehensively studied field in both languages, there are common opinions about their types, classification, and amount of forms.

Resources

1. Abdug‘afforov I. F. O‘zbek tili grammatikasi. –T.: “O‘qituvchi”, 1999. – 238 b.

2. Abdurahmonov G., Rustamov A., Qadimgi turkiy til. –T.: “Fan”, 1982. – 216 b.
3. Abdurahmonov G., Shukurov SH., Mahmudov Q. O‘zbek tilining tarixiy grammatikasi. –T.: “O‘zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati”, 2008. – 320 b.
4. Feyda Umarbek. O‘zbek va uyg‘ur tillarida o‘tgan zamon fe’llarining badiiy nutqda ishlatilishi: Filol. fan. nomz. ...diss. –T., 1998. –102 b.
5. 久野ススム『日本文法研究』(大修館)#ススム=日+章. 1973. - 318 p.
6. 井上優 (2001) 中国語・韓国語との比較から見た日本語のテンス・アスペクト」『月刊言語』12月号